

EU-FarmBook

Funded by
the European Union

The platform is being developed to test a big idea:

Can all the tangible outputs of EU-funded research and innovation projects be brought together and organized in one user-friendly platform to help get practical knowledge into the hands of the farmers, foresters, and other rural actor across Europe who need it most?

The EU-FarmBook Platform is ready for Contributors and progressively for all users:

Can all the tangible outputs of EU-funded research and innovation projects be brought together and organized in one user-friendly platform to help get practical knowledge into the hands of the farmers, foresters, and other rural actor across Europe who need it most?

We need you!

Let's cultivate knowledge together

A **Contributor is the main contact** between a project and EU-FarmBook:

- ✓ Provider of practical project outputs.
- ✓ Partner or Coordinator from Horizon 2020, and Horizon Europe Cluster 6 projects.

Ready to contribute?

Not sure which projects' outputs to choose?

- ✓ Does it **address** potential needs of **farmers or foresters**? Is the information practical to support their daily activities?
- ✓ Is the project output in **any of these formats**: text document, video, presentation, podcast, image, software application, or dataset?

If the answer is positive, then you know it's the right output to upload to EU-FarmBook.

INTERESTED IN MAXIMISE YOUR IMPACT AND MAKING YOUR EU HORIZON / OPERATIONAL GROUP PROJECT RESULTS MORE ACCESSIBLE AND VISIBLE?

CONTRIBUTE NOW!

The EU-FarmBook is an under-development, easily accessible and user-friendly EU-wide digital platform for practitioners in agriculture, forestry, and other rural sectors. It supports the exchange of knowledge among all EU and national AKIS actors.

Why should you contribute?

- ✔ Free maintenance-hosting and open-access
- ✔ Domain Specific
- ✔ Platform funded and endorsed by the EC
- ✔ Project visibility and findability
- ✔ Support Center
- ✔ Easy upload process (manual or via API integration/connection).
- ✔ Integration of practice oriented materials
- ✔ Respects Authors Rights

Future Functionalities

What to expect?

- ✔ Join a community of peers
- ✔ Leveraging AI chatbot support

Multilingual Support:

- **2024:** Upload in all EU languages.
- **2025:** Platform interface accessible in all EU languages.
- **2026:** Content from selected practice-oriented materials automatically translated into 3 languages and English.
- **2027:** Content from selected practice-oriented materials automatically translated into more than 3 languages and English.

Join the Community!

The EU-FarmBook platform:

Is the **one-stop-shop** for the **free** exchange of practical project outputs from all Horizon Cluster 6 Research & Innovation projects.

Ensures different upload options: easily contribute manually or via API for efficient sharing.

Upholds **strict criteria** as a reliable repository, including **metadata**, standardized data, curation, persistent identifiers, online interaction, long-term preservation, and data access conditions.

Recognizes the value of **Open Science**, advocating for the early and widespread sharing of publicly funded research.

eufarmbook.eu

*EU-FARMBOOK IS A DATABASE OF AGRICULTURAL AND FORESTRY INFORMATION, **NOT** A DISTRIBUTION CENTER FOR OUTPUTS*

EU-FarmBook Ambassadors

Meet the Ambassadors team, which aims to **support Contributors** (Partners or Coordinators of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Cluster 6 Research & Innovation projects) and **facilitate connections** with the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) in each Member State:

welcome.eufarmbook.eu/engage

EU-FarmBook Partners

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About the **project**: welcome.eufarmbook.eu
Explore the **platform**: eufarmbook.eu

